

STUDIES ON THIOARSENITES. PART I. PRECIPITATION AND DISSOLUTION OF ARSENIOSULPHIDE

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The interaction between an arsenite and the hydrosulphide has been shown to occur in a number of steps forming thioxy and thio compounds before the precipitation of As_2S_3 which occurs only in acid medium because of the decomposition of the molecular thio-acid, the anions being stable, and not decomposing into As_2S_3 . In alkaline medium the reaction is ionic in nature, *i.e.*, with increasing acidity of the medium, the formation of AsS_4^{5-} is enhanced. Further, the increase in hydrogen-ion concentration will depress the dissociation of the thio-acid, forming molecular H_6AsS_4 which decomposes to H_2S and As_2S_3 .

But the reaction between arsenious acid and H_2S -water, specially in presence of acids, is mainly molecular and arsenic is completely precipitated with only three mols. of H_2S .

It has been further shown that the dissolution of arsenious sulphide occurs by the interaction with HS^- ions; and it proceeds very rapidly to completion as soon as sufficient HS^- ions are available to produce an AsS_4^{5-} ion, and is complete only when four mols. of $NaHS$ to each of arsenic atom are present in the system.

In previous publications Taimni and Agarwal (*Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1953, 9, 116) have shown that elements such as As^V , Mo^{VI} , Pt, Au and other elements of the arsenic group are completely precipitated as sulphides by the decomposition of their thio salts with acids, which are formed by the interaction of alkali sulphides with solutions containing these elements. This fact has been utilised for the quantitative estimations (Taimni and Agarwal, *ibid.*, 1953, 9, 121, 203; 1954, 10, 312; Salaria, *ibid.*, 1956, 15, 514) and separations (Taimni and Srivastava, *ibid.*, 1956, 15, 517; Salaria, *ibid.*, 1957, 16, 3) of such elements as As, Se, Te, Sb, Sn, Mo etc., as sulphides. Some such compounds have also been prepared, isolated and studied by previous workers (*vide Mellor*, "A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", 1929, Vol. IX, pp. 289-90, 315, 532, 569), but the chemistry of these thio salts in solution, the mechanisms of their formation and specially their decomposition by acids leading to the precipitation of metallic sulphides are still obscure. The present paper deals with the formation of thioarsenites, and their decomposition with acids.

It has been found that the precipitation of arsenic trisulphide from an arsenite solution by decomposing its thio salt with acid is complete only when the amount of the hydrosulphide reagent added in the mixture is sufficient to give a ratio of $As:S=1:4$, a value, much higher than that required to form As_2S_3 . It appears that with the progressive addition of $NaHS$ solution to an arsenite solution, thioxy-arsenites are formed, *viz.*, $Na_3H_2AsSO_3$, $Na_4HAsS_2O_2$ and Na_5AsS_2O , the final product being the thioarsenite, Na_6AsS_4 . All these salts exist in a state of equilibrium. The corresponding thio-acids are formed when these salts are decomposed by acids, and arsenious sulphide precipitates only from the thio compound, but not from the thioxy compounds.

Similar conclusion is arrived at when arsenious acid solution is treated with water, saturated with hydrogen sulphide gas. However, from arsenious acid, arsenic

is completely precipitated with only three mols. of hydrogen sulphide gas, because the reaction between arsenious acid and hydrogen sulphide solution, specially in acidic medium, is predominantly molecular in nature, whereas sodium arsenite and NaHS react through their ions. The precipitation of arsenious sulphide from the thio-acid is mainly governed by the p_H of the solution, because it so appears that the dissociation of this acid must be suppressed to form the molecular thio-acid, which decomposes into arsenious sulphide and H_2S . One more interesting feature of these thioxy acids is that with the increase in the number of sulphur atoms in the molecule by continuous replacement of oxygen atoms, the acid character increases.

Dissolution studies of arsenious sulphide are also in conformity with the above facts. These indicate that dissolution occurs through the action of hydrosulphide ions on arsenious sulphide, and it proceeds very rapidly to completion as soon as sufficient HS^- ions are available to produce an AsS_4^{5-} ion, and is complete only when four mols. of NaHS to each of arsenic atom are present in the system. In earlier stages, some polysulphide anions containing some H_2S molecules with them as $H_3S_2^-$ ($HS.H_2S$) $^-$, $H_3S_3^-$ ($HS.2H_2S$) $^-$ may also be formed.

In incomplete precipitations, when the amount of sulphur added as hydrosulphide is less than four times the arsenic, some arsenic escapes precipitation and passes into the filtrate in the form of thioxy compounds, which are liable to atmospheric oxidation to thioxyarsenates, liberating sulphur. This oxidation reaction is more rapid in the case of thioxy anions and at higher temperatures, and in consequence, sulphur is associated with the precipitates of arsenious sulphide, specially at higher temperatures. The separation of sulphur is being studied in greater detail, and the results will be communicated in a future publication.

EXPERIMENTAL

A 0.5M stock solution of Na_2HAsO_3 was prepared by dissolving arsenious oxide in NaOH, and arsenious acid solution was prepared by boiling a weighed quantity of As_2O_3 in water. Both the solutions were standardised iodimetrically.

The reagent sodium hydrosulphide was prepared by saturating a standard 0.1M NaOH solution for about 15-20 minutes with H_2S gas, the sulphide estimated iodimetrically, and the solution made up by a calculated amount of 0.1M-NaOH solution, so that the final solution contained sodium and sulphur in the ratio of 1 : 1.

Similarly, water was saturated with H_2S gas for about half an hour. The sulphide was estimated and diluted to give a 0.05M- H_2S water. Both the sulphide reagents were freshly prepared, and always standardised before use. A. R. chemicals were used in all these experiments.

Precipitations with varying amounts of NaHS.—A standard 0.1M sodium arsenite solution (10 c.c.) was taken and treated with varying amounts (viz. 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 c.c.) of the standard 0.1M-NaHS solution. The thioarsenites so formed were decomposed with an excess of HCl, and the precipitates of arsenious sulphide filtered through a weighed sintered glass crucible (porosity G₄), washed thoroughly with water,

alcohol and CS_2 , successively, dried at $100-10^\circ$, and weighed. The results, when graphically represented, show that the precipitation is complete when the ratio of As : S = 1 : 4.

Precipitation by varying amounts of HCl.—In this set of experiments a standard $0.05M$ sodium arsenite solution (10 c.c.) was treated with a known excess of $0.1M$ -NaHS reagent (25 c.c.). The thio salt so obtained in solution was decomposed by varying amounts of $0.1M$ -HCl, and the arsenic trisulphide, if present at all in the colloidal state, was coagulated by adding 2 c.c. of an 1% BaCl_2 solution. The precipitates so obtained were collected and weighed after suitable treatment. The results, when represented graphically, show that the precipitation starts when all except one sodium have been neutralised, and is complete when so much of hydrochloric acid has been added as to neutralise all the sodium present therein, e.g. in this case 7 mols. of HCl, indicating the important role of the acid concentration in the precipitation of arsenious sulphide from the thio salt.

Precipitation by H_2S -water.—In these sets of experiments the standard $0.05M$ arsenious acid solution (10 c.c.) was taken and treated with varying amounts of $0.05M$ H_2S -water so as to give thio-acids having sulphur in the ratio of 1, 1.5, 2, 3 and 4. In order to study the effect of p_n on the precipitation, this was adjusted by adding NaOH or HCl solution as the case might be. The arsenious sulphide, which appeared in the colloidal state, was coagulated by adding 2 c.c. of an 1% BaCl_2 solution. The precipitates so obtained were collected and weighed after suitable treatment. The results, graphically represented in Fig. 1, indicate the following :

FIG. 1

(i) Amounts of arsenious sulphide precipitated go on increasing as the amount of sulphur added as H_2S is increased, so that the precipitation is complete when As : S = 1 : 3. For the amounts of H_2S added, smaller than the above ratio, the precipitates are always less than the theoretical value for the production of arsenious sulphide by the amount of sulphur introduced.

(ii) The precipitation is a function of the hydrogen-ion concentration.

(iii) The curves of 1, 1.5 and 2 moles of H_2S show maxima at $p_H 4$, which may be due to the association of Ba^{2+} ions with the precipitate during the process of coagulation. At lower p_H values, the colloidal matter produced is small because of the coagulation by hydrogen ion itself, so that the adsorption of barium ions becomes negligible.

(iv) The amounts precipitated by 1, 1.5 and 2 moles of H_2S are respectively about 0.5, 0.66 and 0.75th fractions of the total arsenic, *i.e.*, it is much less than the theoretical value, if calculated on the basis of arsenic trisulphide, but more if calculated on the basis of the thio-acid.

It thus shows that the precipitation occurs by the decomposition of the thio-acid. Since these reactions are reversible in nature, some of the liberated H_2S produces more of the thio-acid molecules to afford the precipitate of As_2S_3 . It appears that by the addition of acid, the equilibrium is shifted in such a way that it produces the undissociated thio-acid molecules, and as these decompose, more, of the thio-acid molecules are produced from the thioxy ones.

Dissolution Studies of Arsenious Sulphide.—The reverse process (*i.e.* the dissolution of arsenious sulphide by H_2S or alkaline H_2S) has also been studied. For this purpose, a solution of H_2S -water, and other reagent mixtures were prepared in such a way that all contained 0.02M sulphide concentration with varying concentrations (0.002M–0.02M) of NaOH. Such reagent mixtures (100 c.c. each) were added to 0.0615 g. of arsenious sulphide, *i.e.* containing 0.0005 g. atom of arsenic in the reaction mixture. The mixtures were shaken well and left overnight. It was observed that with (0.002M–0.01M-NaOH, 0.02M- H_2S) reagent mixtures, at first a yellow colour developed, but after some time the solutions became colorless. Only colloidal sulphur separated out due to oxidation of the polysulphide anions of the type ($H_2S_2^-$, $H_2S_3^-$ etc.) present in the mixture. Beyond (0.01M-NaOH, 0.02M- H_2S), the solutions remained colorless throughout; only arsenious sulphide dissolved slowly, leaving a small amount of unchanged As_2S_3 and a little of sulphur in the residue. With only H_2S -water, a yellow coloured solution with sufficient undissolved arsenious sulphide was obtained.

The unchanged residues were filtered through weighed sintered glass crucibles (porosity G 4), washed thoroughly with water, alcohol and CS_2 successively, dried at 100–10° and weighed. The amounts dissolved or peptised were obtained by difference.

In another set of experiments 2 c.c. of an 1% $BaCl_2$ solution was added to prevent peptisation. The results, thus obtained, show the amounts dissolved due to true salt formation. All these results are graphically represented in Fig. 2, which shows that:

(i) Dissolution of arsenious sulphide occurs mainly through the action of HS^- ions on the precipitate, and it proceeds very rapidly to completion as soon as sufficient HS^- ions are available to give an AsS_4^{5-} ion (*viz.* beyond the point of 0.012M-NaOH, where about 2.5 mols. of NaHS are present per each arsenic atom present as sulphide)

and is complete where 4 mols. of NaHS are present to each arsenic atom in the system.

FIG. 2

(ii) The H_2S molecules have got a peptising effect on arsenious sulphide. This dissolution due to peptisation is prevented by adding barium chloride, and the second curve represents the dissolution due to true salt formation.

(iii) It is observed that apart from peptisation effects, some arsenious sulphide is dissolved in H_2S -water. It is due to the HS^- ions present in H_2S -water, though in a very minute quantity.

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